

Statistical Mechanical Properties of the Quantum Oscillator?

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In a previous note on the quantum harmonic oscillator, it was seen that for the ground state $(-1/2m) d/dx d/dx W_0(x) + .5kx^2 W_0(x) = .5 \omega W_0(x)$ with $W_0(x) = C \exp(-.5 \sqrt{km} x^2)$. Thus, a Gaussian wavefunction cancels the potential term $.5kx^2 W_0(x)$. For an excited state of the form $H_n(x)W_0(x) = \text{wavefunction}$, the second derivative with respect to x yields a term proportional to $H_n(x) d/dx d/dx W_0(x)$ which will again cancel $.5kx^2 W_0(x)H_n(x)$. Thus, the cancellation of $V(x)$ is due to $W_0(x)$. $H_n(x)$ (a hermite polynomial) on the other hand couples with W_0 in the kinetic energy calculation to create more energy. In order for the Schrodinger equation to hold, this coupling must be proportional to: constant $W_0(x)H_n(x)$, with the constant being the extra energy i.e. that beyond the ground state. In this note, we wish to examine the quantum oscillator in terms of statistical mechanical ideas. For the ground state, $W_0(x)W(x) V(x)$, in the Schrodinger equation, is equivalent to $-b W_0(x)W_0(x) \ln(W_0(x)W_0(x))$. Thus, one has an equation containing Shannon's entropy and $\exp(-.5\sqrt{km} x^2)$ has the appearance of an extremum solution. The kinetic energy and potential energy densities may also be written in terms of statistical density functions such as entropy and free energy. When one considers higher energy levels, it seems the statistical mechanical forms of the ground state remain, although they are modified by an overall factor of $H_n(x)H_n(x)$. Thus, even though the full Shannon's entropy for the excited state is $-H_n(x)H_n(x)W_0(x)W_0(x) \ln[H_n(x)H_n(x)W_0(x)W_0(x)]$ only a piece of this is included in quantum mechanical expressions. The term proportional to $\ln[H_n(x)H_n(x)]$ is dropped. Again, $W_0(x) = C \exp(-.5\sqrt{km} x^2)$, even though the energy is higher, and this still has the appearance of an extremum solution, but only of an entropy involving $W_0(x)$. We suggest that in quantum mechanics (at least in the oscillator case), there may be extremization of a portion of entropy rather than the full Shannon's entropy. This seems to make it complicated to discern the statistical mechanical nature of quantum mechanics.

Quantum Mechanical Oscillator

The Schrodinger equation for an oscillator may be solved to yield $E_n = \hbar \omega (n + .5)$ with $\omega = \sqrt{k/m}$ and $W_n(x) = W_0(x) H_n(bx)$ where $H_n(bx)$ is a hermite polynomial, b a constant and $W_0(x) = C \exp(-.5\sqrt{km} x^2)$. When dealing with excited states, the creation operator approach is usually used. In ((1)), we argue that the term $.5 kx^2 W(x)$ may be cancelled by a term of the kinetic energy, namely $(-1/2m) H_n(x) d/dx d/dx W_0(x)$, so it seems the resonance created with the potential is really based on $W_0(x)$. That does not mean $H_n(x)$ does not play an important role. It seems it is like an oscillation which supplies the extra energy for the higher energy level. It also seems $H_n(x)$ forms its own resonance with $W_0(x)$ at the kinetic energy level i.e.

$$(-1/2m) [W_0(x) d/dx d/dx H_n(x) + 2 [d/dx W_0] [d/dx H_n(x)]] = \text{constant} H_n(x) W_0(x) \quad ((1))$$

One may see that $H_n(x)$ as a hermite polynomial satisfies ((1)).

Statistical Mechanical Picture of the Oscillator Ground State

In another note (2), we argue the ground state of the oscillator Schrodinger equation is linked to statistical mechanics because $.5 k x^2 \psi(x)\psi(x) = -b \psi(x)\psi(x) \ln[\psi(x)\psi(x)]$ which is proportional to Shannon's entropy. The solution $\exp(-.5 \sqrt{km} x^2)$ has the appearance of an extremum of entropy subject to constraints. Thus, one may argue that the ground state quantum oscillator may be thought of in terms of statistical mechanical ideas. Furthermore, $f_p^* f_p = \exp(-c p^2)$ and $\psi(x)\psi(x) = \exp(-d x^2)$ with c and d being constants, which has the same form as classical statistical momentum and spatial probabilities.

One may consider writing changes in kinetic and potential energy densities in statistical mechanical terms. The overall energy density is $E \psi(x)\psi(x) = E \text{ density}(x)$ so the first order overall change is: $E \frac{d}{dx} \text{ density}(x)$.

Potential energy density = $.5k x^2 \psi(x)\psi(x) = -b \text{ density}(x) \ln[\text{ density}(x)] = b$ (entropy density)

The kinetic energy density should then be of the form:

$E \text{ density}(x) - b$ (entropy density) = Free energy density with b as a temperature

Thus, even though the overall energy density is $E \text{ density}(x)$, the kinetic and potential energy densities may be written in statistical mechanical terms for the ground state.

One may further show that:

Potential energy density = $[\frac{d}{dx} \text{ density}] [.5m v(x)v(x)]$ and

Kinetic energy density = $[\frac{d}{dx} \text{ density}] [V(x)]$ ((2))

Here $.5m v(x)v(x)$ is the classical kinetic energy and $.5mv(x)v(x) + V(x) = E$.

Excited Oscillator States

What happens if one considers excited oscillator states, namely $W(x) = \psi(x) H_n(x)$?
The overall energy density is still $E_n \text{ density}(x)$ although now $E_n = \hbar \omega (n + .5)$ instead of $\hbar \omega .5$ as it did for the ground state.

Potential energy density = $-b H_n(x) H_n(x) [\text{ density ground}(x)] \ln [\text{ density ground}(x)]$

Similarly,

$$\text{Kinetic energy density} = H_n(x)H_n(x) [E_n (\text{density ground}(x)) - b \text{ entropy ground } (x)] = H_n(x)H_n(x) [\text{Free energy ground } (x)]$$

Thus, kinetic and potential energy densities are still in a statistical mechanical form in terms of the ground state, but are modified by an overall factor of $H_n(x)H_n(x)$. The ground state density is still given by $C \exp(-.5 \sqrt{km} x^2)$ which has the form of an extremum of a ground state entropy equation subject to constraints. Thus, the physical system may still be obeying some kind of maximization of entropy subject to constraints, but only using the ground state entropy which is part of Shannon's entropy.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Shannon's spatial entropy} &= H_n(x)H_n(x)W_0(x)W_0(x) \ln [H_n(x)H_n(x)W_0(x)W_0(x)] \\ &= H_n(x)H_n(x)W_0(x)W_0(x) \{ \ln(H_n(x)H_n(x)) + \ln(W_0(x)W_0(x)) \} \end{aligned}$$

Normally, in statistical mechanical problems, one maximizes the full Shannon's entropy, not a portion. It seems that in the oscillator problem, one maximizes only a portion as it is only a ground state wavefunction which forms a resonance with the potential. The $H_n(x)$ forms a resonance with $W_0(x)$ in terms of kinetic energy and supplies extra energy to the system. Thus, it may be that quantum mechanics does make use of the extremization of entropy for excited states (and also ground states), but does not necessarily extremize the full Shannon's entropy. Thus, one is forced to find the appropriate statistical quantity (say entropy or wavefunction) in a quantum problem. For the oscillator, this seems to be $W_0(x)$, the ground state wavefunction. An alternative argument might be that one should not consider the Schrodinger equation in statistical mechanical terms at all, however, for the ground oscillator $V(x)W_0(x)W_0(x)$ is proportional to Shannon's entropy. We argue this is more than an coincidence.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we examine the ground oscillator in terms of statistical mechanical ideas. We then try to apply these to excited states and find statistical mechanical quantities for the ground state solution are still present in the problem. The full wavefunction is $H_n(x)W_0(x)$ and the ground state potential and kinetic energy densities may be written in statistical terms as $b [\text{ground state Shannon's entropy for } W_0]$ and ground state free energy density for W_0 , but with a modification by the factor $H_n(x)H_n(x)$. Thus, we argue, even though the full Shannon's entropy expression for $W(x)=H_n(x)W_0(x)$ exists, only a portion of it is used in the quantum oscillator problem, even for excited states. It seems entropy extremization still occurs, as $W_0(x)=C \exp(-.5 \sqrt{km} x^2)$, but this extremization is based only on the ground state Shannon's entropy. If this is the case, a statistical mechanical approach to quantum mechanics is complicated as one must determine which "entropy" is extremized in a quantum problem. This, in turn, may involve separating the wavefunction into different factors, of which only one is involved in a statistical mechanical process involving extremization of entropy.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Quantum Excited States (preprint, zenodo, 2019)
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Gaussians as Solutions of the Schrodinger Equation and Maximum Entropy Calculations (preprint, zenodo, 2018)